

TANGENT – Beyond Transportation Dashboarding

Tiago Dias^{1*}, Hannah Tune², Antonio Masegosa^{3,4}, Athina Tympakianaki⁵, Ynte Vanderhoydonc⁶, Leire Serrano³, Ana V. Silva¹, Lara Moura¹

1. A-to-Be, Mobility Technology, Portugal

2. Transport for Greater Manchester, United Kingdom

3. DeustoTech, Faculty of Engineering, University of Deusto, 48007 Bilbao, Spain

4. IKERBASQUE, Basque Foundation for Science, 48011 Bilbao, Spain

5. Aimsun, Barcelona, Spain

6. University of Antwerp - imec, IDLab - Faculty of Applied Engineering, 2000 Antwerp, Belgium

Correspondence*: tiago.delgado.dias @a-to-be.com

Abstract

The transportation sector has been facing intense pressure for the last decades as it is a central aspect to the adequate functioning of cities and people's lives. TANGENT intends to shift cities to multi-modal cooperative transportation operation, acting and planning strategically. With this, it intends to promote the optimisation of the cities' transport networks, resulting in a sustainable modal-shift to public transport and light last mile solutions. This article presents the TANGENT project, highlights operational challenges from one of its trial cities and shows how the TANGENT tool will work, how it addresses these operational challenges and the architecture that will be used for its implementation.

Keywords:

Multimodal Transport Strategic Management; Dashboards for Advanced Network Transport Management Services

Introduction

The transportation sector has been facing intense pressure for the last decades as it is a central aspect to the adequate functioning of cities and people's lives.

Transport networks have historically been managed in a segmented way, with each operator managing their own transport mode. Multi-modal cooperation is still more common in aspects like interfacing modes and unifying ticketing, and not so usual at operational and strategic levels. Municipalities and local transport agencies are changing this reality by introducing multi-modal network visualisation, monitorisation and some level of operation. TANGENT intends to materialise this by implementing and trialling a Cooperative Multi-modal Transport Operation tool, referred to as the TANGENT tool. TANGENT intends to shift cities to multi-modal cooperative transportation operation, acting and planning strategically.

TANGENT is a project funded by the European Commission under the Research and Innovation Programme Horizon 2020. The project started in September 2021 and will end in August 2024. TANGENT is developing new complementary Information and Communication Technology (ICT) tools for optimising traffic operations in a coordinated and dynamic way from a multimodal perspective and considering automated/non-automated vehicles, passengers, and freight transport. TANGENT is coordinated by the University of Deusto, based in Bilbao, Spain. The pilot cities involved are Lisbon, Great Manchester, Rennes, and Athens. TANGENT will allow the precise knowledge and management of the mobility flows among the transport modes and will enable the implementation and integration of innovative mobility solutions, services and business models. TANGENT is helping the pilot cities achieve a 10% reduction travel time, an 8-10% reduction in CO2 emissions, a 5% reduction of accidents, 10-15% increase in use of public transport [1].

TANGENT will improve knowledge and management of mobility flows along a range of transport modes. In addition, it will enable the implementation and integration of innovative mobility solutions, services and business models. The project will contribute to more efficient traffic management, facilitating multimodal networks, accelerating the transition towards connected and automated mobility, reducing pollutant emissions and congestion, improving safety and security, and reducing the cost of mobility for all.

The paper is structured as follows. First, it presents the TANGENT project approach. Then it highlights the main operational challenges from one of its trial cities. Subsequently, it presents how the TANGENT tool will work, how it addresses these operational challenges and the architecture that will be used for its implementation.

The TANGENT Project approach

The main concept behind the project idea is to orchestrate and coordinate the different transport modes and systems for synchronising and optimising the overall transport network and deliver, as a result, new methodologies, models and techniques to support efficient traffic operations in the multimodal transport network in a dynamic and adaptive way. These methodologies models and techniques are described below.

Figure 1 – TANGENT concept overview

It will include dynamic mechanisms to replicate users' decisions in the presence of unexpected events and system disruptions. The goal is to describe how individual needs, preferences and sentiments affect travel related decisions and how mobility patterns change under various system conditions such as the emergence of new services and new travel mode alternatives, network interventions and road pricing policies.

Traffic Network prediction & simulation models aims to infer the future traffic state in the network by predicting multimodal travel demand and supply, and mobility parameters (such as road or public transport occupancies) for different time-horizons. It will incorporate and fuse knowledge derived from travel behaviour models and exploit machine learning techniques to feed traffic simulation software to estimate the impacts of events in the traffic network. Two major items will be delivered: predictions of multimodal travel demand and supply characteristics, and an efficient simulation framework that can be used to model and analyse the impact of optimised transport measures under recurrent and non-recurrent supply/demand patterns (e.g., events).

Transport network optimisation: optimisation of multimodal network-wide traffic management will be implemented based on Artificial Intelligence, and concretely model-based optimisation and reinforcement learning techniques. The module will use the current status of the traffic, as well as the predictions and simulations of the future evolution of traffic to determine the best possible actions that can be taken depending on the performance targets, constraints and scenarios considered by stakeholders (e.g., Traffic Managers & Fleet Operators). The potential management strategies and actions will be defined by a set of decision variables over which stakeholders of Connected and Cooperative Automated

Mobility (CCAM) can influence transport supply, e.g., traffic control, CCAM services, and the transport demand, e.g., public transport incentives.

TANGENT will deliver a set of applications for decision-making support creating a framework for coordinated Network Transport Management (NTM), encompassing an enhanced mobility information service and dashboard. The functionalities are:

(a) Enhanced information service for multimodal transport management – Dashboard & API, it will integrate information from different modes (cycling, scooters, micro-mobility, public transport, train, demand-responsive transport, car-sharing, car-polling, connected and automated vehicles, ferries, etc.), both from public and private stakeholders. This information will be provided in a single dashboard for traffic managers, and through APIs to transport operators, service providers and transport users.

(b) Real-time Traffic Management Services, based on the traffic and transport information provided in the “Enhanced information service for multimodal transport management – Dashboard & API”, TANGENT will provide recommendations at operational/ tactical level to transport agents, with the aim of optimizing the overall transport network operations on a day-to-day basis.

(c) Transport network optimisation for Transport Authorities, aims to support decision-makers at the strategic and tactical level for producing policies or response plans that contribute to optimize the performance of the network, including dynamic transport network management and transport supply optimisation. Furthermore, this service will allow the simulation of different “What-If” scenarios, showing how the transport network performance would be affected under certain hypothetical circumstances.

Operational Challenges

To assist efficient multimodal network management across Greater Manchester, Transport for Greater Manchester (TfGM) operates a 24/7 Control Centre. The control centre plays a major role in the operation and management of the city/region's highways network, also having a key role in managing events and incidents and ensuring network resilience. In addition to the management of the highway, information is gathered from across bus and Metrolink (tram) to ensure the transport network is operating efficiently. An extensive network of monitoring infrastructure facilitates the collection, analysis, and use of data to understand how and where people are travelling. This allows minimising network and service disruption and providing customer information.

TfGM has sophisticated traffic management systems and means of data gathering. However, it presents gaps in how the data and traffic management systems are used to control the transport network, as a whole. TfGM has the ambition (outlined in the Greater Manchester Transport Strategy 2040) [2] to move toward a fully integrated transport network with a ‘One Journey’ approach so customers can move seamlessly between transport modes. To allow this, there is a need to maximise the opportunities of increasing data, connectivity, and future mobility systems, as well as it is imperative to enhance the integration of new and existing traffic management tools and data streams.

It was already understood that the management of a transport network requires multi-actor participation. For this reason, within TANGENT, extensive engagement with stakeholders for each city case study is being carried out. Multi-actor cooperation for the Greater Manchester case study involves TfGM teams and stakeholders participating in a three-stage workshop process. To date, two stages of this engagement have taken place. This process enables a deeper understanding of the challenges faced in the day-to-day operation and management of the transport network from a multimodal perspective [3]. It allows effective communication between TANGENT service development and the various actors involved in the case studies. Furthermore it addresses the specific requirements of the transport network, considering the involved stakeholders and local policy goals. The outcomes of the initial workshop process have supported TfGM in reaching a common understanding and agreement of the case study’s objectives and scope, defining which transport modes and network elements should be involved in the implementation of each TANGENT service. Also outlining the key target users of the TANGENT services, the expected impacts, and benefits of such an implementation. A specific outcome of the workshop process for TfGM, was the identification of three key challenges to efficient network management:

- Integration of systems and a ‘one network’ status view– currently operators are required to gather data from numerous systems to understand and dynamically intervene in incidents, events and congestion.
- Lack of automation – operator intervention is required in many decision-making processes. Data is generated from several systems but the capacity for data-led automated processes is currently not available to a high enough standard to be trusted.
- Technical staff are required for many traffic management operations, for example, reviewing signal control. This means skilled resources are required to be called upon by network operators. Simplified dashboards, integration and automation would mean less reliance on skilled staff that are currently in demand and hard to recruit.

Aligning these challenges to the development of TANGENT Services will be crucial to the success of TANGENT.

Dashboarding for Transportation

Operational and strategic Dashboards are common interfaces used to convey a unified status of entire transportation networks, either for a specific operator or for several (or all) modes in an entire city. When designing a Dashboard, it is essential to select which information should be visible, how it should be arranged and, very importantly, how it should be represented, namely how it’s drawn over a map or how an indicator is colour coded. The combination of the previous criteria with the customisation (manual or automatic) of the dashboard to specific user roles is the key to a successful Dashboard implementation.

Some dashboards, like the TANGENT one, also include interactive functionalities like incident management or simulation. The interactive elements are a challenge for the dashboard design. A key factor here is in-context visualisation, which can benefit interactions by showing the visualisation elements at the locations of interest to support decision and accompany the execution of actions.

The SETA H2020 project [4] was dedicated to large scale mobility monitoring and planning and outputted several considerations regarding the visualisation of transportation data which are explored next.

Most transportation data is either geospatial or temporal data, and in some cases both (spatio-temporal data). The obvious choice for geospatial data representation are maps. One of the most critical aspects to manage when displaying transportation data on maps is the granularity of the information depicted. If the granularity is low (detailed), the information will probably be difficult to understand at a macro / city-wide level but might be adequate for viewing at a greater zoom level, namely door-to-door or street level. Using different levels of data aggregation, at different zoom levels, is usually key to providing the most adequate adaptive visualisation. One aggregation method is achieved through the usage of heatmaps, where instead of drawing individual occurrences, like incidents or trips, a colour depicting the occurrence count is used for each location. This technique is especially effective to represent overlapping movement or trajectories at a macro level and without filtering (which is another technique that can greatly help with interactive visualisation).

As for temporal data, the typical visualisation options are histograms and timelines, covering most of the needs of these kind of data types.

Finally, for the combined spatio-temporal data SETA proposes the usage of 3D visualisation (with time being the z-axis dimension). In TANGENT, 3D visualisation will not be explored but instead browsable timelines will be used as these may provide a simpler and more intuitive way for users to understand spatio-temporal information.

One important challenge big data has for visualisation, is the sheer amount of data and how it makes it difficult to prepare intuitive visualisations without first summarizing the data itself. This challenge is mostly addressed by aggregation techniques, which involves losing detail. To counterbalance that, most robust visualisation platforms also include a drill-down functionality, be it done through zooming in on a map, by hovering over a data representation or by clicking on it. The balance between aggregation for overview and interaction methods, like zoom or click, to get detail, is one of the most relevant aspects of data visualisation and exploration.

Another key aspect for visualisation is filtering. Filtering information will remove data that is

unnecessary for the user viewing the system, helping to focus attention. This is especially important when there is a given context, like the management of a scenario / incident. Given a particular context, it is possible to represent the specific geographical area affected, display only information on specific transport modes instead of all of them, etc. Filtering information is also valuable because it can decrease the volume of information to be processed by the system.

Furthermore, SETA also proposes the usage of animations to emphasise new information arrival and the usage of data processing parallelisation to increase performance.

Some public and private Transportation dashboards [5] [6] [7] [8] were analysed to identify patterns that are more effective in conveying different types of information, also contributing to the TANGENT Dashboard design. One main aspect in most Transportation Dashboards is the importance of combining multi-source, multi-modal live data. In addition, colour coding is an important aspect of Dashboard design, making use of the intuitive meaning behind colours. Most Dashboards analysed make an intensive use of maps, except for the first one [5] which uses mostly KPIs and camera images. KPIs are great at providing very quickly readable city-wide indicators. Camera images provide a local view of different city locations, camera images might work well in smaller city dashboards but in larger cities providing a more complete picture through traffic status over maps might be a better solution. Camera images can always be available to get more details and visual validation for a particular location, this is done in other Dashboards, namely in [7]. The map views are usually very intuitive and help in quickly getting an overview of different systems. They also have the advantage of allowing the combination of different information in the same map. Tabular views can provide more details that are not directly possible to convey over a map. They can be used directly in higher level views or be accessible as a detail for map elements. Histograms are also an important tool when it comes to understanding trends and comparing the current situation to the past.

The TANGENT Dashboard

The TANGENT Dashboard is the key user interface for transport operators and managers, from the stakeholders involved in the Case Studies of TANGENT. Benefiting from the examples of existing public and private Dashboards and from the framework of transport information representation provided by the SETA project, this section presents an initial version of the TANGENT’s user interface (UI).

The Dashboard is the central page of the user interface. It shall provide a live view, customised for each user, showing widgets with the most relevant data items for the Case Study and for the modes that are most relevant for the logged-in user. It shall provide visibility for tools like Notifications and Chat and provide navigation to all other areas.

Figure 2 - Initial version of the Dashboard interface

Figure 2 proposes an initial version of the Dashboard interface. On the left side it illustrates an example

of a navigation panel for all the functionalities that should be available for the user. The centre and right areas display an arrangement of widgets that can be edited, meaning the user could swap widget positions, replace widgets with other ones, add new widgets and remove existing ones. In normal visualisation, the widgets can allow interaction (e.g., zooming or panning a map), but should also include a way to open that single widget in the dedicated Visualiser screen.

The Visualiser screen will show the opened visualisation but it shall allow the user to select other visualisations to display. Visualisations can be of a single data item or of more than one combined, when it is a map visualisation. The Visualiser should also provide filters to apply to the visualisation, namely for selecting which measurements from the data item are visible (e.g., occupancy, speed, etc.) and for other aspects like date and time. The Visualiser shall allow the visualisation of data in map and tabular views. Tabular views can use colour coding according to rules for easier results comprehension.

The TANGENT Dashboard will not only cover visualisation and monitoring but it will also include strategic multi-mode, multi-entity operational features like Smart Network Load Balancing (SNLB), Cooperative Incident Management (CIM) and Simulation of Predefined scenarios.

The simplest feature is the Simulation of Predefined scenarios which consists of preparing a transport model for the simulation of a specific scenario. The simulation results are then viewable in the Dashboard interface. SNLB and CIM share many common aspects, both are used to cope with specific degradations of the transport conditions, they are prepared in a planning phase where a transport model is prepared to provide optimised responses for specific transport scenarios. Both SNLB and CIM will monitor the current transport status for breaches of normal transport conditions to trigger specific response plans that resulted from the planning phase. The main difference is that in SNLB only a single actor from a single entity is involved in the process whereas in CIM several actors from different entities cooperate in decision points both in CIM planning and operation.

To better support these more interactive features, the Dashboard includes a notification feature that, among other things, alerts users to breaches in normal transport conditions as part of SNLB and CIM and, also, a chat feature. The chat feature allows two types of interaction, one is ad-hoc chatting among users or created groups, and the other is a contextualised chat group that is created automatically for a CIM operation.

Most Transport Dashboards are focused on visualisation and monitoring as presented in the previous section. The SETA European project as well as others explored Transport visualisation and monitoring deeply, providing valuable results which we incorporated into the TANGENT Dashboard design. This provided TANGENT with robust visualisation and monitoring features that are then used as the basis of more complex, higher-level interactive strategic decision support features like SNLB, CIM and Simulation. With these features, TANGENT goes beyond the typical monitoring dashboard to become a responsive integrated transport management tool, capable of optimising a complex transport network with appropriate multi-entity user interaction.

Transport operators usually have their own operational tools and dashboards. These share many common features with the TANGENT Dashboard like Monitoring, Incident Management and activation of Response Plans. Nevertheless, these operational tools are usually limited to operating and optimising a specific transport mode instead of providing the fully multi-modal, multi-entity holistic approach that is supported in TANGENT. Transport Dashboards usually provide an integrated, multi-modal perspective but don't offer any operational capabilities. On the other hand, Transport Operational tools and Dashboards provide the operational capabilities but usually for a specific operation and usually only for a single transport mode. The TANGENT Dashboard brings these operational features to a multi-modal, multi-entity platform, bridging the gaps in both existing approaches. This is what defines the TANGENT Dashboard as a Next Generation Traffic Management System (NGTMS).

To conclude, it is important to validate if TANGENT can address adequately the main challenges identified by TfGM for their Control Centre's current traffic management systems, as they are common to many Traffic Management Centres. The first one was about the lack of integration between different tools used in the Control Centre and the impossibility of having a single unified status view. The TANGENT Dashboard will provide this kind of unified view, overcoming the first challenge from TfGM. The second challenge is the lack of automation in decision-making. This is partly addressed by the SNLB and CIM functionalities in TANGENT. It is only partly addressed because it is the position of the TANGENT consortium that it is a crucial element to keep humans in the decision-making loop even when the system can automate the generation and recommendation of multi-modal response plans, as TANGENT does. Adopting such an approach will immediately contribute by identifying anomalous

circumstances in which the system proposes a response plan and by creating the base content of that response plan. Human operators will determine if the response plan is adequate, otherwise, they will change it to cope with specificities the system might not have taken into account. From the operational experience of using such a solution, it will be possible to further refine the quality of the automated response plans and it will be clearer whether the automated response plans are adequate for unsupervised usage or not. It is also important to note that TANGENT will not implement the actions from the response plan but only publish them as information that can be used by the external systems to adopt the response plan. If this integration is achieved, then the third challenge posed by TfGM regarding the need for technical staff for many traffic management operations will also be overcome by TANGENT. This need for technical staff will thus be shifted from operations to planning.

The TANGENT Architecture

To achieve the proposed features and position itself as a Next Generation Transport Management System, the TANGENT Dashboard is implemented as part of a full software architecture covering components for data exchange (API), data processing, transport simulation and human decision support.

Figure 3 presents the high-level technical architecture diagram for the entire system.

Figure 3 - TANGENT Top-level technical architecture

The top-level technical architecture diagram depicts the main system components of the TANGENT Platform and their main integrations. It also identifies the Services each component belongs to with an S<number> label next to the component.

TANGENT relies on external Data Sources to collect their data. This is the responsibility of Service 0 – Data Collection. These sources are either accessed by Service 0 to collect data or the sources access Service 0 to deliver the data. Service 0 then harmonises the data and delivers it to Service 1 through an API.

Service 1 centralises data exchange between the different system components as well as towards the exterior (not represented in Figure 3), whereas Service 0 gets all exterior data. Service 1 also includes the Dashboard which is the TANGENT User Interface. It naturally consumes data from the TANGENT API. Service 1 also includes a component that is responsible to extend the collected data from Service 0 with calculated, forecasted and predicted data. It’s the Data Processing, Critical Conditions and Supply Forecasting component.

Service 2 includes support for SNLB and CIM. SNLB and CIM are similar processes used to address network issues and incidents tactically and strategically. They are both based on Service 3 templates, the Common Operational Picture (COP) for CIM and the Response Plan Package (RPP) for SNLB. The COP and the RPP can be seen as templates to define the response plans and its activation conditions. They start by notifying about specific degrading conditions and then suggest a response plan for those situations. Their purpose is to address and solve the causing situations and resume normal operations.

The User Interface for SNLB and CIM is implemented in the Dashboard but is supported by the SNLB and CIM component inside Service 2. The integration between the Service 2 components and the Dashboard is achieved through the TANGENT API.

Finally, Service 3 offers Network Optimisation features, namely supporting the COP production for CIM and RPP production for SNLB in Service 2. Service 3 also offers a Simulation functionality to analyse What-If predefined scenarios.

Figure 4 (below) presents a more detailed technical architecture showing internal components of each module and how they integrate through the TANGENT API.

Figure 4 - TANGENT Detailed Technical architecture

The TANGENT API receives data from Service 0, stores it in a Document Database and exposes it for usage by Services 2 and 3, internally in Service 1 for the Dashboard and for external and public access. The JSON format is used for the communication between Service 0 and Service 1 and the TANGENT API is a set of REST APIs adopting the JSON format. This will allow the TANGENT API to be fully compliant with the OpenAPI specification [9] to use well defined data schemas (JSON Schema [10]) and to store data directly using a Document Database.

Service 0 will exploit the RDF standard [11] to guarantee syntactic and semantic interoperability of metadata and data sources requiring a harmonisation process. The JSON-LD W3C specification [12] defines a JSON-based format to serialize RDF data and will be exploited to encode harmonised and/or fused data in a JSON-compliant format following the defined data schemas.

Service 1 will consume data from Service 0 using an AMQP message queue. In case the message payload is too large for the message queue, a URL will be published instead of the data itself and Service 1 will fetch the data from an HTTPS server hosted by Service 0.

The TANGENT API, as part of Service 1, exposes all data using both its REST API and an AMQP message queue. The same data is available to be fetched from the REST API and is published to the message queue where it can be consumed by subscriptions.

The Dashboard consumes Static, Dynamic and Calculated data using the message queue for all. Dynamic data and events are consumed by the Data Processing, Critical Conditions and Supply Forecasting module using the message queue. Calculated data is produced by this module and sent to the REST API. Service 2 consumes Calculated data and events and produces specific Calculated data which allows it to synchronise with the Dashboard. All communication with the Service 2 module is achieved through the message queue. Likewise, Service 3 also consumes Calculated data and events and produces Calculated data for synchronisation with the Dashboard. The Network Optimisation modules in Service 3 are hosted locally at each Case Study city. This is necessary because they will host the

Transport Simulator instances (e.g., Aimsun Next, PTV Vissim or Visum) used for optimisation and simulation. Most Transport Simulators cannot run on shared cloud servers, with each user having their license installed locally. Additionally, city specific transport models may not be kept outside the city server scope for privacy and security reasons. This is supported by TANGENT API design, as each Network Optimisation module will only subscribe events for its city, query the REST API for local city data and deliver local calculated data to the REST API.

Figure 5 presents the technological solutions chosen for the different components in Service 1 and 2 which are hosted on the AWS cloud. The other components will be hosted locally by partners and are not covered here.

Figure 5 - Detailed deployment architecture for AWS

Service 2 comprises the simplest technological solution depicted. It uses AWS Elastic Kubernetes Service to implement a managed, auto-scalable containerizing solution where it hosts Java applications that run using OpenJDK.

This same base is used in the API and Dashboard components. The API will implement its REST API using VERT.X and possibly also the Raw Data Proxy. Amazon MQ is used as an AMQP Broker for the API Events component. It will use mongoDB Atlas as its cloud database as a service.

The Dashboard is the most complex module. It includes an Apache Tomcat webserver where the Dashboard web application is hosted. This web application will be built using a JavaScript framework to choose between React, Angular or Vue. On top of this JavaScript framework there will be a Dashboarding solution that will include customisation functionalities and other features necessary for the Dashboard. For visualisation of the Dashboard components, specific integrations and plugins of the Dashboarding solution will be used alongside with ClickSense for data processing and analysis. For map visualisation and interaction Leaflet and OpenStreetMaps will be used. Finally, to implement the Chat feature, a third-party solution like Vonage will be used. It will also use MongoDB Atlas [13] as its cloud database as a service.

Several AWS services are used for monitoring all the other modules. AWS IAM is used for user and permissions management and authentication and access control to all TANGENT modules. AWS Shield, WAF and Amazon API Gateway are used to expose all of TANGENT’s public internet interfaces in the TANGENT API (across all three technologies supported) and the Dashboard web interface. Grafana will be receiving events from all TANGENT modules to monitor application health and operations. With this, it will provide application health and management dashboards.

The option for AWS services like Amazon MQ, AWS Elastic Kubernetes Service or mongoDB Atlas is crucial for the seamless scalability and adaptation of the TANGENT solution to different workloads during its development and trialling phases. It will also simplify deployment and some aspects of

implementation.

Conclusions and Future Work

Addressing modern city transportation challenges needs to be done in a strategical, multi-modal way, with decision making and support tools that span and coordinate the multiple entities involved. TANGENT is an EU funded project that aims to explore and tackle this holistic need by developing and trialling a strategic multi-modal operations platform across four large European cities. The main aspect in this platform is that it will not only focus on information visualisation and exploration but it will also offer cooperative operational functionality, backed by decision support systems that are based on simulation. By bringing together information from the different modes of transport in the cities and with these cooperative features TANGENT should address the main Operational Challenges currently faced by city transport operators and management entities like TfGM.

The large volume of data involved and coordinating incident responses between several entities are significative demands for the platform and user interface. This justifies a straightforward architecture that allows the platform to scale with changing data volumes and demand. Therefore, elastic cloud services make-up a significative part of the supporting platform for the TANGENT tools' implementation and deployment.

2023 will be an intense development and early testing year for the TANGENT project, spanning all four main Services (0 to 3). The interactive iterative process of developing, trialling and evaluating functionalities within the Case Studies will be crucial for the success of the project.

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